

Applied heat exchanger network retrofit for multi-period processes in industry: A hybrid evolutionary algorithm

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ABSTRACT

In Swiss process industry, process integration is often applied to retrofit existing plants with multi-period operation. Such periods may experience a high degree of variation in temperature or mass flow. Some process streams may not exist in every period or are soft streams. The resulting retrofitted network needs to be able to ensure feasible heat transfer in each period by the integration of mixer configurations to control the temperature. These attributes increase the complexity of the solution space. Hence, this work proposes an evolutionary two-level algorithm for heat exchanger network retrofit. Genetic algorithm is used for topology optimization and a differential evolution algorithm handles the heat loads. The algorithm is extended with practical constraints such as a maximum number of heat exchangers. Explicit mixer temperature calculations are implemented using the Lambert W-function. The algorithm was successfully applied to an industrial case study, reducing its total annual cost by approximately 66%.

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1. Introduction

With the growing awareness on the need to mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and the inevitable depletion of fossil fuel, the world is transitioning towards more sustainable and energy-efficient alternatives. The current global focus is to optimize energy production and consumption with their associated sustainability and environmental impacts, which provides industry the incentive and necessary policies to improve their processes (Zore et al., 2017). The European Commission established a set of binding measures to help the EU to reach its energy efficiency target by 2030, where EU countries will have to achieve energy savings of at least 0.8% each year for the period of 2021–2030 (European Commission, 2020). To offset the deficit, one of the key steps is to increase energy efficiency (Maus et al., 2020). The Swiss industrial sector is responsible for 18% of total Swiss energy con-

sumption, with more than half used for process heating, contributing 20% to Swiss CO₂ emissions (Kemmler and Spillmann, 2020). Since industry is a major consumer in the Swiss energy system, optimizing heat recovery (HR) is the first crucial step in achieving deep decarbonization. One methodology addressing this challenge is Process Integration, which was developed during the oil crisis in the 1970's. The methodology focused on reducing hot and cold utility consumption to help improve energy efficiency and energy savings. Reducing process heat demand of industrial processing plants is a critical step for emissions reduction, with multiple long-term economic and environmental benefits. These targets can be realized with heat exchanger networks (HEN) (Klemeš, 2013). Most current project improvements are dedicated to retrofitting of existing industrial plants rather than grassroots design. As a result, the focus of this contribution is on HEN retrofit of multi-period processes in industry. The chemical, pharmaceutical, food, and beverage industries cover 45% of the total Swiss energy for process heat demand (Kemmler and Spillmann, 2020). These processes often have multiple periods due to production of multiple products in the same plant as well as seasonal changes in ambient temperatures.

Numerous studies have been carried out to improve the efficiency of HEN design. There are three notable methods to

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Sets

$C = \{0 \dots j \dots NC\}$	Set of cold streams
$CH = \{1 \dots ch \dots NCH\}$	Set of heat load chromosomes
$CT = \{1 \dots ct \dots NCT\}$	Set of topology chromosomes
$E = \{0 \dots e \dots NE\}$	Set of heat exchangers
$H = \{0 \dots i \dots NH\}$	Set of hot streams
$K = \{0 \dots k \dots NK\}$	Set of enthalpy stages
$GH = \{1 \dots gh \dots NGH\}$	Set of heat loads generations
$GT = \{1 \dots gt \dots NGT\}$	Set of topology generations
$OP = \{0 \dots op \dots NOP\}$	Set of operating periods

Parameter

A	Heat exchanger area (m^2)
C	Cost coefficient (CHF)
CR	Crossover probability (-)
c	Specific cost coefficient (e.g., CHF/ m^2)
c_p	Specific heat capacity (kJ/kg K)
f_d	Degression factor (-)
H	Enthalpy flow (kW)
HoF	Hall of fame list (-)
h	Film heat transfer coefficient (W/(m^2 K))
i_r	Interest rate (-)
$LMTD$	Logarithmic mean temperature difference (K)
MT	Mutation probability (-)
\dot{m}	Mass flow (kg/s)
n	Deprecation lifetime (y)
\dot{Q}	Heat flow (kW)
T	Temperatures ($^{\circ}C$)
TAC	Total annual costs (CHF)
U	Overall heat transfer coefficient (W/(m^2 K))
W	Lambert W-function (-)
w	mass fraction (-)

Greek letters

Δ	Penalty constant (-)
ΔT	Temperature difference (K)
Δt	Time duration (s)
ψ	Temperature difference ratio (-)

Subscripts

a	Annualized
c	Cold side
h	Hot side
in	Inlet
out	Outlet
S	Supply
T	Target

Abbreviations

CU	Cold utility
DE	Differential evolution
GA	Genetic algorithm
HEN	Heat exchanger network
HENR	Heat exchanger network retrofit
HENS	Heat exchanger network synthesis
HEX	Heat exchanger
HR	Heat recovery
HU	Hot utility
MINLP	Mixed-integer nonlinear programming
OP	Operating period

retrofit a HEN (Sreepathi and Rangaiah, 2014): 1) Pinch-based HEN retrofit analysis, 2) Mathematical Programming (MP), and 3) hybrid of graphical-insight based and MP approach. Asante and Zhu (1996) developed Network Pinch retrofit, a two-stage pinch-

ing approach that ensures minimal structural changes and capital-energy optimization. Jiang et al. (2014) uses sensitivity analysis to improve HEN energy performance by increasing of HEX area with fixed network structure to improve utility savings. Akpomiemie and Smith (2015) developed a retrofit methodology on the installation of heat transfer enhancement without additional heat transfer area to reduce the implementation time.

Pinch-Analysis (PA) relies on thermodynamic and physical insights of processes to identify the potential energy savings from retrofitting a HEN using graphs (composite curves, grand composite curves). One of the key advantages of this method is the efficient visualization of the problem, which allows stakeholder internal communication and development of practical solutions based on the engineers inputs. There are several developments in the graphical-insight based approach from the recent years. The Retrofit Thermodynamic Diagram (RTD) plots the heat loads and driving forces of the HEN (Lakshmanan and Bañares-Alcántara, 1996), which was later modified to incorporate thermodynamic feasibility representation and minimum allowed temperature difference, known as Shifted RTD (SRTD) (Yong et al., 2014). Yong et al. (2015) later extended the SRTD to include Grid Diagram to accurately visualize the HEN arrangements and key parameters, known as the Shifted Retrofit Thermodynamic Grid Diagram (SRTGD), with the inclusion of maintenance planning by Chin et al. (2020). Wan Alwi and Manan (2010) presented Stream Temperature vs. Enthalpy plots (STEP), a graphical tool that simultaneously carries out targeting and design of HEN, and was further extended to include HEN retrofit by allowing users to simultaneously diagnose and retrofit existing HEN (Lai et al., 2018). Lai et al. (2019) further extends STEP to include heat exchanger (HEX) area versus enthalpy to minimize the overall required HEX area to reduce the payback period. Kamel et al. (2017) presented temperature driving force (TDF) that revamps the graphical approach of Network Pinch (Gadalla, 2015) by structural and non-structural modifications. Bonhivers et al. (2016) links PA and bridge analysis to develop a retrofit tool, energy transfer diagram (ETD), to identify suitable HEN configuration based on the rate of cascaded heat through each existing HEX. Lal et al. (2018) modified the ETD by adding the support of Heat Surplus-Deficit Table for high potential energy savings.

According to Sreepathi and Rangaiah (2014), MP-based methods are generally divided into two optimization methods, stochastic methods or deterministic methods. The focus of the review for MP is only on genetic algorithm (GA) and differential evolution (DE), as this paper develops its method based on those two stochastic algorithms. For more detailed reviews, Sreepathi and Rangaiah (2014) reviewed the different methodologies for retrofits and Toimil and Gómez (2017) reviewed on metaheuristics used for HEN retrofit. The genetic algorithm (GA) is based on the evolution in nature (Holland, 1975). Lewin uses GA to synthesize HENs in a two part series. Lewin et al. (1998) used GA to determine the structure of the HEN and rate the efficiency of the maximum energy recovery units, without resorting to stream splitting. In the second part, Lewin (1998) aimed to obtain a family of cost-optimum HEN where stream splitting was supported.

The optimization of retrofitting of HEN is usually solved with deterministic method, however, due to complex, non-linear, non-convexity of the vast solution space; GA can be applied to solve the problem. Liu et al. (2014) combines GA with deterministic method to solve the mixed-integer nonlinear programming (MINLP) problem of minimizing the cost of newly added HEXs, utilities, and repiping, this is also applied to MINLP problem for retrofitting HEN in crude oil distillation unit (Liu et al., 2016). Björk and Nordman (2005) developed a hybrid optimization method that uses GA and MINLP to solve a large-scale retrofit heat exchanger network problem. GA divides the large retrofit HEN problem into sub-

systems and find the optimal structure for each subsystem. This reduces the computational time and effort for a large-scale optimization problem. Rezaei and Shafiei (2009) retrofits HEN by coupling GA with NLP and ILP. GA is used to produce different networks to find the best structural modifications. Genetic algorithms are typically suitable for structural optimization and are able to avoid being trapped in local optima as shown by Bochenek and Jezowski (2006), where they used GA to solve retrofit problem by considering the actual network and potential savings related to reusing exchanger units. Biyanto et al. (2016) developed a genetic algorithm to solve the NLP formulation of a HEN retrofit with an emphasis on the increase and optimization of the overall heat transfer coefficient using heat transfer enhancement. It was found that coiled wire inserts had the greatest improvement out of all examined enhancement devices.

Differential Evolution, first proposed by Storn (1996), Storn and Price (1997), is a population based algorithm designed to optimize continuous variables such as heat loads. To the authors best knowledge, DE has been applied mostly for HEN synthesis instead of retrofit processes. Yerramsetty and Murty (2008) applied DE to HEN synthesis, where the problem is not decomposed like GA but employs a simultaneous approach to optimize the structure of HEN, heat loads of HEXs, split streams, and minimum approach temperature. Zhang and Rangaiah (2013) applied DE to the case study used by Bochenek and Jezowski (2006), and found the solution to be better by preventing the algorithm from being trapped in a local optima and increase computational efficiency. Aguitoni et al. (2018) used both GA and DE, GA optimizes the variable related to topology and DE optimizes the heat loads and stream split fraction, and found that better or equal total annual cost (TAC) solutions were achieved for the six HEN synthesis case studies.

Most of the reviewed case studies focuses on single period operation. However, industrial processes might exhibit multiple periods over time. Methods to help optimize multi-period design for the retrofit case are needed. Jones (1991) mentioned that HEN design for multi-period processes have three fundamental design types, conventional design, re-sequence design, and re-piping design. Kang and Liu (2014) presented a two-step HEN retrofitting approach for multi-period operations to improve the operational flexibility of the HEN. They used a reverse order matching method, which simultaneously adjust the heat transfer area, re-matching stream, and adjusting the heat transfer area to result in the least increase. They further extended the method to minimize the investment costs by using different strategies to match the heat transfer areas (Kang and Liu, 2015). The strategies applied comprise maximum number of substituted HEXs after retrofit, minimum additional heat transfer areas in the retrofitted HEN, and minimum investment cost for retrofit. The results based on these strategies were reported to be better than other literature results and provide greater benefit for a large-scale HEN retrofit problem in practice. Kang and Liu (2017) also presented a systematic strategy to retrofit multi-period HEN using multi-objective optimization with multiple practical restrictions. The optimized objectives are minimizing TAC and total annual CO₂ emission by providing a Pareto front to represent a series of retrofit targets, and the most desirable option to be selected. Isafiade (2018) applied a reduced superstructure synthesis approach to retrofit of HENs for multi-period operations. Langner et al. (2020) proposed a framework that splits the retrofit process into five sub-steps to reduce the complexity of the problem. The framework derives different design configurations through Pinch based approaches and uses MP to efficiently derive flexible and cost-efficient structural feasible designs. Non-deterministic approaches, meta-heuristics are seldom used for multi-period HEN, the above studies mentioned for GA and DE are only applied to a single OP. Pavão et al. (2018) in-

tegrated a post-optimization (PO) strategy to their two-level meta-heuristic method based on Simulated Annealing and Rocket Fireworks Optimization (Pavão et al., 2017) to allow the method to handle multi-period HEN optimization. With the PO integrated, the solutions presented achieved lower TAC compared to other methods and significantly improve the results. Wang et al. (2021) carried out bi-level optimization strategy that combines binary particle swarm optimization and an Alopex-based evolutionary algorithm to establish a simultaneous flexible HEN model. The flexibility analysis adjusts the HEX areas if a critical point arises during a non-convex problem.

2. Problem statement

The current EnergieSchweiz program is to promote energy efficiency in Switzerland. In industry, one of the methods to improve energy efficiency of industrial processes is retrofit of existing plants. Multi-period operation is common in the Swiss industry and is thus, the focus of this paper. Feasible heat transfer in each OP can be achieved by integrating mixer into the HEN to increase flexibility. Thereby, two mixer configurations are distinguished: bypasses which modify the outlet temperature and admixers which modify the inlet temperature of the heat exchanger. The heat exchanger network optimization in the retrofit process is part of conceptual design and therefore the following assumptions are made: 1) detailed heat exchanger design is not considered in this step; 2) only counter-current heat transfer is possible; 3) all heat transfer coefficients are considered to be constant; and 4) fouling is neglected. These points are to be investigated in a detail design step after the optimization.

The introduction of mixer configurations into the network demand additional practical constraints. By reducing the mass flow, hazardous temperature levels might be point of concerns (e.g., phase change). Therefore, new constraints are introduced that limit the maximum or minimum temperature for each process stream. In industry, often more practical solutions are preferred over the global optimum solution. Therefore, one of the key challenges is to find a local optima which can be practically implemented instead of the global optimum. In addition to the required constraints, practical considerations such as a limited number of HEXs per split are to be considered.

Furman and Sahinidis (2001), showed that the formulation of MINLP HEN synthesis for single period processes is already \mathcal{NP} -hard in the strong sense. In addition, due to the initial HEN design in the retrofit problem, the complexity is increased. The additional constraints as well as the additional dimensions for the multi-period operation, with the possibility to integrate bypasses and admixers, increase the complexity of the solution space which might lead to not finding feasible solutions for large-scale problems at all. Accordingly, stochastic rather than deterministic algorithms are utilized.

In a previous work (Stampfli et al., 2020), a two-level genetic algorithm with differential evolution algorithm was introduced and applied to a small case study from literature. In this work, the algorithm is applied to a more complex case study from industry. Therefore, the algorithm needs to be adapted in order to be able to handle soft streams (non-process streams with no fixed target temperature, e.g., waste gas from a boiler which is emitted to the environment), and streams which are not active in every OP. With the aim to increase practicability of the solutions, integration of bypasses and admixer is analyzed in more detail. Hence, the mixing temperature need to be calculated based on the HEX areas. Further constraints such as extreme stream temperatures (e.g. phase change or equipment constraints) at any mixing point need to be considered. Finally, piping can have a large impact on the retrofit design and, therefore, must also be included.

Fig. 1. Superstructure for retrofit of multi-period heat exchanger networks.

3. Heat exchanger network retrofit model

The retrofit model (see Fig. 1) is based on the stage-wise superstructure (SWS) from Yee and Grossmann (1990). In each enthalpy stage k , every hot stream H_i can be connected with every cold stream C_j . At the end of each stream, an utility re-balancing HEX can be placed to fulfill the energy balance. The mixing process in splits is considered to be isothermal. The SWS is extended with (1) an additional dimension of operating periods (OPs) (e.g., Verheyen and Zhang, 2006) with different process requirements (existence of a process stream, mass flows, specific heat capacities, film heat transfer coefficients) and operation parameter (temperatures, heat loads, mixing fractions), (2) possible utility HEX within each enthalpy stage, and (3) possible mixer (bypass and admixer) for each HEX. The latter increases the flexibility of the network and ensures to achieve the process requirements in each OP.

With a bypass, only a fraction of the mass flow passes through the HEX and is heated up, resulting in a change of the outlet temperature. The remaining partial mass flow and the outlet mass flow of the HEX are mixed together non-isothermally. With an admixer to a HEX, a partial fraction of the outlet mass flow of the HEX is non-isothermally mixed to the inlet mass flow of the HEX. Thereby, the mass flow in the HEX is increased resulting in a change of the inlet temperature.

In contrast to heat exchanger network synthesis (HENS), an initial network of the existing process is given for heat exchanger network retrofit (HENR). Therefore, the minimal number of required enthalpy stages k is given by the existing topology. In an enthalpy stage, each stream can only have one heat exchanger in series. Multiple heat exchangers in parallel are possible with splits. During the retrofit process, the following modifications on the network are possible: (1) re-piping of a HEX, (2) re-sequencing of a HEX, (3) adding area to a HEX, (4) adding a new HEX, and (5) removing an existing HEX.

3.1. Heat exchanger network without mixer

Hot streams H_i are cooled down from the last to the first enthalpy stage. With

$$T_{i,k}^{op} = \begin{cases} T_{i,S}^{op} & \text{if } k = NK \\ T_{i,k+1}^{op} - \frac{\sum_{e \in E_{i,k}} \dot{Q}_e^{op}}{cp_i^{op} \dot{m}_i^{op}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall i, k, op, \quad (1)$$

the temperature of the last enthalpy stage $k = NK$ is equal to the supply temperature of the hot stream. For all other enthalpy stages, the temperatures are given by the enthalpy stage temperatures above and the heat loads within the stages. Thereby, $E_{i,k}$ represents the set of all heat exchangers connected to the hot stream H_i in enthalpy stage k , \dot{Q}_e^{op} the heat load of a heat exchanger e in operating period op , cp_i^{op} and \dot{m}_i^{op} are the given specific heat capacity and mass flow of the process stream in operating period op . In contrast to this, cold streams C_j are heated up from the first to the last enthalpy stage. Therefore, with

$$T_{j,k}^{op} = \begin{cases} T_{j,S}^{op} & \text{if } k = 0 \\ T_{j,k-1}^{op} + \frac{\sum_{e \in E_{j,k}} \dot{Q}_e^{op}}{cp_j^{op} \dot{m}_j^{op}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \forall j, k, oc, \quad (2)$$

the temperature of the first enthalpy stage $k = 0$ is equal to the supply temperature of the cold stream. For all other enthalpy stages, the temperatures are given by the previous enthalpy stage temperature and the heat loads within the stage.

Based on the enthalpy stage temperatures, the required area for each HEX can be determined by

$$A_e = \max_{op \in OP} (A_e^{op}) = \max_{op \in OP} \left(\frac{\dot{Q}_e^{op}}{U_e^{op} \Delta T_{m,e}^{op}} \right) \quad \forall e \quad (3)$$

whereby, A_e is the minimum required area (largest area of all OPs) of a HEX over all operating periods to ensure feasible heat transfer.

Fig. 2. Heat exchanger temperatures.

Fig. 3. Relevant temperature differences for mixer type selection.

U_e^{op} is the overall heat transfer coefficient computed by

$$U_e^{op} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_i^{op}} + \frac{1}{h_j^{op}}} \quad \forall e, op \quad (4)$$

where, h_i^{op} and h_j^{op} are the corresponding film heat transfer coefficients of the connected hot and cold stream. The mean temperature difference in the HEX $\Delta T_{m,e}^{op}$ is determined using the logarithmic mean temperature difference (LMTD) given by

$$\Delta T_{m,e}^{op} = \begin{cases} \frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{op} - \Delta T_{e,2}^{op}}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{op}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{op}}\right)} & \text{if } \Delta T_{e,1}^{op} \neq \Delta T_{e,2}^{op} \\ \Delta T_{e,1}^{op} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad \forall e, op \quad (5)$$

If the temperature differences on both sides of the heat exchanger are equal, there is no need to calculate the LMTD, as the temperature difference between the streams is constant in the whole HEX. The temperature differences on both sides of the HEX are given by

$$\Delta T_{e,1}^{op} = T_{i,k}^{op} - T_{j,k}^{op} \quad \forall e, op \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta T_{e,2}^{op} = T_{i,k+1}^{op} - T_{j,k+1}^{op} \quad \forall e, op \quad (7)$$

under consideration of counter-current operation.

3.2. Heat exchanger and mixer temperatures

Due to the inclusion of a mixer, HEXs can have four different temperatures on each side (see Fig. 2). Thereby, in this work the term mixer configuration, includes the splitter as well as the mixer before and after the HEX. The temperatures upstream and downstream of the mixer configuration are the corresponding enthalpy stage temperature ($T_{i,k}^{op}$, $T_{j,k}^{op}$, $T_{i,k+1}^{op}$, and $T_{j,k+1}^{op}$), which are determined using the energy balance over one enthalpy stage as described in Eqs. (1) and (2) respectively. With a mixer, one of the inlet or outlet temperatures of the HEX ($T_{e,h,in}^{op}$, $T_{e,h,out}^{op}$, $T_{e,c,in}^{op}$, or $T_{e,c,out}^{op}$) can be manipulated. Non-isothermal mixing is considered for the calculation of these manipulated temperatures.

For each operating period in which,

$$A_e^{op} \leq A_e \quad \forall e, op \quad (8)$$

the area A_e^{op} is smaller than the minimal required area A_e , a mixer configuration is needed to achieve the targeted enthalpy stage temperatures. In each of these OPs, the mixer configuration is always chosen to be on the stream with the lower heat capacity flow CP (mass flow changes have a higher impact on the temperature (see Fig. 3)). To decide which mixer configuration is selected, their feasible temperature ranges are compared to each other and the mixer configuration with the larger feasible range is selected. For a bypass on the cold stream, the outlet temperature of the stream is increased by reducing the mass flow passing through the HEX.

To ensure feasible heat transfer, the outlet temperature of the cold stream cannot be increased beyond the inlet temperature of the hot stream. The feasible range of the temperature change for a bypass ΔT_b is shown in the left diagram in Fig. 3. For an admixer on the cold stream, the inlet temperature is increased by increasing the mass flow passing through the HEX. The inlet temperature of the HEX for the cold stream cannot be increased above its outlet temperature, therefore, the feasible range for the temperature change of an admixer ΔT_a is, in this case, the change in temperature of the cold stream in the HEX. The right diagram in Fig. 3 shows the same concept for a mixer on the hot stream. An exception to this concepts, are HEXs with zero heat load in an OP connected to an active stream. In this case, the stream needs to be fully bypassed.

In each operating period one mixer temperature ($T_{e,c,in}^{op}$, $T_{e,c,out}^{op}$, $T_{e,h,in}^{op}$, or $T_{e,h,out}^{op}$) has changed and needs to be determined. However, these new mixer temperatures cannot simply be calculated because the LMTD (Eq. (5)) cannot be solved explicit for one of the temperature differences ($\Delta T_{e,1}^{op}$ or $\Delta T_{e,2}^{op}$). These temperature differences are usually determined using an approximation (Chen, 1987). However, Chen (2019) has proposed an explicit solution approach using the Lambert W-function (Lambert, 1758; Euler, 1779). This work uses the explicit solution. The adapted derivation for the application of the Lambert W-function to the logarithmic mean can be found in Appendix A. The Lambert W-function is computed using the Python library Scipy (Virtanen et al., 2020). The procedure for bypass on a hot stream is shown below. Thereby, $T_{e,h,out}^{op} \neq T_{i,k}^{op}$ because of the reduced mass flow through the HEX. To determine the new value of $T_{e,h,out}^{op}$ the procedure is applied as follows:

1. Determine the new LMTD for the given operating period by

$$LMTD^{op} = \frac{\dot{Q}_e^{op}}{U_e^{op} A_e} \quad (9)$$

whereby, A_e is the needed minimum area which ensures feasible heat transfer for every OP.

2. Calculate the temperature difference ratio between the known temperature difference and the LMTD:

$$\psi_2 = \frac{\Delta T_{e,2}^{op}}{LMTD^{op}} \quad (10)$$

3. Thus, the Lambert W-function is ill-defined (the solution can be on two different branches W_0 and W_{-1} and the point between those), there are three different cases which need to be considered depending on ψ_2 .

- (a) If the LMTD is equal to the known temperature difference ($LMTD^{op} = \Delta T_{e,2}^{op}$; $\psi_2 = 1$), the temperature difference is constant in the HEX. In this case the unknown temperature

difference is given by:

$$\Delta T_{e,1}^{op} = \Delta T_{e,2}^{op} \quad (11)$$

- (b) If the LMTD is smaller than the known temperature difference ($LMTD^{op} < \Delta T_{e,2}^{op}$; $\psi_2 > 1$), the solution is on branch W_0^- :

$$\psi_1 = \frac{-W(-\psi_2 e^{-\psi_2}, W_0^-)}{\psi_2} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta T_{e,1}^{op} = \psi_1 \Delta T_{e,2}^{op} \quad (13)$$

- (c) If the LMTD is larger than the known temperature difference ($LMTD^{op} > \Delta T_{e,2}^{op}$; $\psi_2 < 1$) the solution is on branch W_{-1} :

$$\psi_1 = \frac{-W(-\psi_2 e^{-\psi_2}, W_{-1})}{\psi_2} \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta T_{e,1}^{op} = \psi_1 \Delta T_{e,2}^{op} \quad (15)$$

4. The new mixer temperature is determined by replacing $T_{i,k}^{op}$ with $T_{e,h,out}^{op}$ in Eq. (6):

$$T_{e,h,out}^{op} = T_{j,k}^{op} + \Delta T_{e,1}^{op} \quad (16)$$

3.3. Total annual cost

Total annual cost of the HEN is given by

$$TAC = \frac{i_r (1 + i_r)^n}{(1 + i_r)^n - 1} C_{cap} + C_{op,a} \quad (17)$$

whereby, i_r is the interest rate and n the depreciation period. The capital costs C_{cap} are given by

$$C_{cap} = \sum_e (C_{HEX,e} + C_{mix,e} + C_{split,e} + C_{move,e} + C_{match,e}) \quad (18)$$

The HEX costs $C_{HEX,e}$ are given by

$$C_{HEX,e} = C_{0,e} + C_{A,e} (A_e - A_{e,init})^{f_{d,e}} \quad (19)$$

whereby, $C_{0,e}$ are the base costs, $C_{A,e}$ the specific costs per area, and $f_{d,e}$ the degression factor which decreases cost per area as area increases for a particular HEX. If an existing HEX is removed, the costs are given by

$$C_{HEX,e} = C_{0,e} + C_{R,e} A_{e,init}^{f_{d,e}} \quad (20)$$

whereby, $C_{R,e}$ is a specific removal cost per area of the HEX. Additional mixer costs $C_{mix,e}$, and split costs $C_{split,e}$ are fixed costs independent from the area. However, the cost for adding and removing can be different. Further costs for re-piping and re-sequencing $C_{move,e}$ are also constant coefficients per HEX. Each of these cost coefficients can be adapted for every HEX separately. Additional match costs $C_{match,e}$ are considered for HEX that are far apart. Due to the fact, that these costs are highly plant layout dependent (e.g. additional drilling), no equation is provided here. The cost for each match is a constant user input value. The annual operating costs $C_{op,a}$ are given by

$$C_{op,a} = \sum_{op \in OP} \left(c_{HU} \left(\sum_{e \in E_{HU}} \dot{Q}_e^{op} \Delta t^{op} \right) + c_{CU} \left(\sum_{e \in E_{CU}} \dot{Q}_e^{op} \Delta t^{op} \right) \right) \quad (21)$$

whereby, c_{HU} and c_{CU} are specific utility cost per energy, Δt^{op} the operating period duration. E_{HU} and E_{CU} are the sets of hot and cold utility HEXs.

4. Evolutionary optimization approach

The model formulated in Section 3 is a MINLP formulation which is at least \mathcal{NP} -hard in the strong sense. Therefore, a stochastic optimization algorithm with two levels is used (Stampfli et al., 2022). The algorithm is developed in Python and available under an open source license (Stampfli, 2021). The algorithm is based on evolutionary concepts using a GA for the topology optimization (discrete variables) on the top level and on the sub level a DE for the optimization of the heat loads. In Fig. 4, an overview of the algorithm is provided. The constraints used in both algorithms are described in Section 4.1. The procedure is as follows. First, a random population of topologies is initialized and checked for feasibility. Thereby, the topology is checked for exceeding the allowed number of HEXs in a split as well as for connections between utility streams. These constraints are evaluated previously in order to reduce unnecessary computation of infeasible solutions. Instead of applying the DE for heat load optimization and the evaluation using the HEN model, a penalty function, which results always in higher TAC than the initial solution, is applied to compute the objective.

In a next step, all feasible solutions are distributed to the available CPU cores, and for each topology, a random population of heat loads is initialized. Thereby, the maximal and minimal possible heat load of each heat exchanger is constrained by a stream dependent on the maximal heat load and a user defined minimum heat load. Next, all heat load populations are evaluated and checked for feasibility. Thereby, the objective is the TAC as described in Section 3.3. The constraints for the DE evaluation are the energy balances of each process stream in every OP and positive temperature differences for each HEX. Further, mixer temperatures, cannot exceed or fall below stream specific extreme temperatures (e.g., phase change or equipment constraints). Costs for infeasible solutions are evaluated with another penalty function. In the DE, the three evolutionary operators' mutation, crossover, and selection are performed to optimize the heat loads. The termination criteria for the DE are a maximal number of generations and a maximal number of generations without improvement. After the DE, the best solutions are stored in a Hall of Fame list, which is always updated as soon as a better solution is found. As long as the termination criterion of a maximal number of topology generations is not fulfilled, the evolutionary operators (selection, crossover, and mutation) are executed, and new modified topologies are evaluated by checking for feasibility and optimizing the heat loads with the DE.

4.1. Constraints

In order to provide feasible and practical solutions the use of some constraints is essential. To reduce the search space, the connection between utility streams is forbidden. The user has to set the maximal number of total possible HEXs. Splits in a HEN increase the complexity of the network and the controllability of the system. Therefore, an additional constraint limiting the number of possible HEX in a split is provided for the user to decide on the desired complexity of the system:

$$\sum \#E_{i,k} \leq \#E_{max} \quad \forall i, k \quad (22)$$

$$\sum \#E_{j,k} \leq \#E_{max} \quad \forall j, k, \quad (23)$$

whereby $\#E_{i,k}$, $\#E_{j,k}$ are cardinalities of the sets of HEXs on hot i or cold j stream in the enthalpy stage k . $\#E_{max}$ is a user defined variable and represents the maximal possible number of HEX in a

Fig. 4. Overview of the evolutionary algorithm.

split. The heat load of each HEX is limited to

$$\dot{Q}_{\min} \leq \dot{Q}_e^{op} \leq \dot{Q}_{e,\max}^{op} \quad \forall e, op \quad (24)$$

whereby, \dot{Q}_{\min} is a user defined variable and $\dot{Q}_{e,\max}$ is given by

$$\dot{Q}_{e,\max}^{op} = \min(\Delta\dot{H}_i^{op}, \Delta\dot{H}_j^{op}) \quad \forall e, op \quad (25)$$

whereby the enthalpy flows of the process streams are given by

$$\Delta\dot{H}_i^{op} = c_{p,i}^{op} \dot{m}_i^{op} (T_{i,S}^{op} - T_{i,T}^{op}) \quad \forall i, op \quad (26)$$

$$\Delta\dot{H}_j^{op} = c_{p,j}^{op} \dot{m}_j^{op} (T_{j,T}^{op} - T_{j,S}^{op}) \quad \forall j, op. \quad (27)$$

Non-negative re-balancing utilities at the end of the streams is ensured by the energy balance given by

$$\Delta\dot{H}_i^{op} - \sum_{\forall e \in E_i} \dot{Q}_e^{op} = \dot{Q}_{CU}^{op} \geq 0 \quad \forall i, op \quad (28)$$

$$\Delta\dot{H}_j^{op} - \sum_{\forall e \in E_j} \dot{Q}_e^{op} = \dot{Q}_{HU}^{op} \geq 0 \quad \forall j, op. \quad (29)$$

whereby, E_i and E_j are the sets of all HEXs on the hot i or cold j stream. In order to ensure feasible heat transfer in each HEX, the temperatures on both sides of the HEX need to be positive which is given by

$$T_{e,h,in}^{op} - T_{e,c,out}^{op} \geq \Delta T_{\min} \quad \forall e, op \quad (30)$$

$$T_{e,h,out}^{op} - T_{e,c,in}^{op} \geq \Delta T_{\min} \quad \forall e, op. \quad (31)$$

The minimal temperature difference ΔT_{\min} is a user defined variable. If there is a mixer additional temperature constraints need to be considered. For admixers a positive temperature difference within the stream needs to be ensured for hot streams by

$$T_{e,h,in}^{op} - T_{e,h,out}^{op} > 0 \quad \forall e, op \quad (32)$$

and for cold streams by

$$T_{e,c,out}^{op} - T_{e,c,in}^{op} > 0 \quad \forall e, op. \quad (33)$$

For bypasses, additional stream specific extreme temperatures, which cannot be exceeded, need to be considered, given by

$$T_{e,h,out}^{op} - T_{i,extr} > 0 \quad \forall e, op \quad (34)$$

$$T_{j,extr} - T_{e,h,out}^{op} > 0 \quad \forall e, op. \quad (35)$$

For evolutionary algorithms there are various constraint handling techniques such as penalizing or decoding strategy (Talbi, 2009). In this case, constraints on topology modifications (Eqs. (22) and (23)) are based on the penalizing strategy. The distance to the feasible solution is used to guide the algorithm to the feasible region. This is achieved by a penalty function which replaces the objective if the solution is infeasible. The quadratic penalty function

$$h = \Delta + (x_{feas} - x)^2 \quad (36)$$

is used. The value Δ is a penalty constants which ensure that every infeasible solution is more expensive than the worst feasible solution. The distance to the feasible solution $(x_{feas} - x)$ is squared, since the optimum of a quadratic function is easy to find. For constraining the heat loads (Eq. (24)) the decoding strategy is used. This means, that the algorithm cannot create solutions in the feasible region. This is achieved only by allowing to select a random value between \dot{Q}_{\min} and $\dot{Q}_{e,\max}^{op}$. Equations (28) to (31) are constraints which are often violated. Therefore, the penalizing strategy is applied.

5. Industrial case study - potato chips production

The developed algorithm is applied to a straightforward and realistic industrial case study to guide the readers application of the optimization. A potato chips production plant from the Zweifel Pomy-Chips AG (ZPC) is analyzed (Fotsch, 2006). ZPC is a Swiss food company, producing snacks such as potato chips. The frying process (fritter line 1) for the potato chips has a heating demand of around 64% of their total heating demand.

5.1. Process description

The fritter line 1 (see Fig. 5), is used to fry two varieties of potato chips: (1) Regular chip (oil mass fraction $w_{oil} = 35\%$; 4'410 h/y) and (2) cractive chips (oil mass fraction $w_{oil} = 25\%$; 2'610 h/y). The HEN needs to be flexible to cover both OPs. The core operation of the process is the frying of the raw chips. The main heating demand is to maintain a constant temperature of the frying-oil. Therefore, a separate utility system consisting of a natural gas boiler is installed. Hence, this match is considered to be fixed and not a process requirement. With the fried chips, a fraction of the frying-oil is removed. Therefore, a make-up-oil feed is

Fig. 5. Flow chart of the Fritter-line 1 plant for chips production at Zweifel. Stream temperatures correspond to the two OPs: regular chips / cractive chips.

needed which is pre-heated by hot utility to the frying temperature (C_3). The vapor (C_1) of the fritter is used as additional fuel for the boiler. In order to reduce the natural gas demand, the boiler waste gas (H_1) is used to heat the fritter vapor (C_1) and the boiler supply air (C_2). After frying, the chips are cooled down by cold utility to room temperature (H_2). For the production of the cractive chips, the degreaser is in operation to reduce the oil mass fraction of the fried chips. Hot air (C_4) and direct steam (C_5) are used to reduce the oil content. The heating of the air, as well as the evaporation of the direct steam is covered by hot utility. In the cractive chips production, the frying-oil temperature is reduced from 176 °C to 166 °C. Due to this, most temperatures of the cractive chips production are lower as in the regular chips production. The waste gas stream (H_1) from the natural gas boiler is a soft stream. After the heat recovery (vapor heating and boiler supply air heating), the waste gas can be optionally cooled down to 30 °C.

In Appendix B, the corresponding process requirements of the fritter line 1 for both OPs are shown in Table B.3. The utility data is shown in Table B.4 and the equipment modification cost is shown in Table B.5. Lang factors of 1.1 and 3.0 are assumed for the removal of existent and the installation of new equipment, respectively (Lang, 1948). Table B.6 shows the match cost between the streams. The existing HEN is shown in Fig. 6.

5.2. Algorithm configuration

For the GA, a population of $NCT = 100$ chromosomes is initialized. During the tournament selection, the best of $NT = 5$ chromosomes is chosen. To monitor the best solutions, the $HoF = 10$ best solutions are stored in the Hall of Fame list. Crossover is performed with a probability of $CR = 90\%$ and mutation is performed with a probability of $MT = 10\%$. For the GA, $NGT = 50$ are performed before termination. For each feasible GA chromosome, a DE population of $NCH = 200$ chromosomes is initialized. With a probability of $CR = 90\%$ crossover is performed. The perturbation factor is set to $F_p = 0.5$. The DE is terminated after $NGH = 100$ generations or $NGHOP = 5$ generations without improvement.

The algorithm was executed on a Linux based server with 256 GB RAM, 128 threads distributed over 64 CPU cores. Thereby, the feasible GA chromosomes are distributed to all threads to run the DE and evaluate the solution.

6. Results

To evaluate the case study, the manual case study parameters were chosen as follows: minimal temperature difference $\Delta T_{min} = 2$ K, minimal heat load $Q_{min} = 10$ kW, cost penalty $\Delta = 500,000$ CHF/y. First, in Section 6.1 the best found solution is ana-

Fig. 6. Initial HEN design with two process internal HEXs. Heat loads are given below each HEX corresponding to the two OPs: regular chips / cractive chips. The outlet temperature of the soft stream H_1 is given as well.

lyzed by its comparison to the initial design. Thereby, the topology modifications, the heat load, area changes, and the resulting cost are analyzed.

Section 6.2, analyzes the performance of the algorithm as well as its sensitivity depending on the number of possible HEXs, enthalpy stages, and allowed HEXs per split.

6.1. Best found solution

The topology of the best found solution is shown in Fig. 7, whereby it cannot be guaranteed that this is the global optimum but rather a local optimum. The number of possible HEXs within the process was set to $NE = 7$, the number of enthalpy stages to $NK = 3$, and the number of possible HEX within one split to $\#E_{max} = 2$. The retrofitted design resulted in one HEX being removed (HEX 2) and six new are being added (HEX 3–6). The topology of HEX 1 is not modified (no re-piping, re-sequencing with only one existing HEX is not possible). The new HEX, number 5, is directly connected to hot utility. All the other HEXs require a mixer to ensure feasible heat transfer in each OP. The admixer for HEX 1 and 4 have a very low mixer fraction. Such admixers are unlikely to be implemented and the heat balance is rather fulfilled

Fig. 7. Best found HEN design with six process internal HEXs. Heat loads are given below each HEX corresponding to the two OPs: regular chips / cractive chips. The mixing fractions for each mixer as well as the outlet temperature of the soft stream H₁ are shown. Stream C₅ is a steam evaporation (x is the vapor fraction).

Table 1
Comparison of heat loads and areas between the best found solution and the initial solution.

HEX	Initial design			Best found design		
	\dot{Q}_e^1 kW	\dot{Q}_e^2 kW	A_e m ²	\dot{Q}_e^1 kW	\dot{Q}_e^2 kW	A_e m ²
Process HEX						
1	234	245	16.0	232	242	15.2
2	46	45	2.5	-	-	-
3	-	-	-	0	171	8.3
4	-	-	-	44	44	5.7
5	-	-	-	0	13	0.4
6	-	-	-	0	245	19.1
7	-	-	-	46	22	10.3
Balance utility HEX*						
CU ₁	-	-	-	-	-	-
CU ₂	101	69	5.6	11	3	1.4
HU ₁	-	-	-	2	3	0.1
HU ₂	-	-	-	2	2	0.1
HU ₃	56	26	0.8	11	4	0.2
HU ₄	0	247	4.8	0	2	0.1
HU ₅	0	188	0.5	0	4	0.1

Balance utility HEX number is corresponding to the connected process stream (e.g., CU₁ at the end of H₁).

by utility compensation. HEX 3 and HEX 6 need to have a bypass because they are connected to cold streams which are only active in one OP.

By comparing the topology to the initial design (see Fig. 6), it can be seen that in the new design, every stream (except soft stream H₁) is in need of a balancing utility HEXs. However, the heat loads of all utility HEXs are small, or even negligible. Furthermore, more waste heat from the soft stream is recovered. In the initial design 280 kW in OP1 and 290 kW in OP2 are reused, resulting in a total of 1990 MWh/y. In the retrofitted design, 232 kW in OP1 and 658 kW in OP2 are reused, resulting in a total of 2740 MWh/y. As a result, the outlet temperature is for OP1 slightly increased from 261 °C to 264 °C and for OP2 decreased from 250 °C to 224 °C.

The changes in heat loads and the resulting area are given in Table 1. HEX 1 is the only reused HEX. The area does not need to be extended. The heat loads of the balance utility HEXs are reduced significantly by increasing the heat loads of the process in-

ternal HEX. Also HEX 5, which is connected to hot utility, is rather small compared to the other process internal HEXs. Therefore, it can be said that the HR of the process is exploited quite well. The two new balance utility HEX HU₁ and HU₂ are rather small (heat load of 2 kW to 3 kW). By a manual post-optimization, analyzing loops and paths within the network, such HEXs are likely to be avoided. E.g., by reducing the outlet temperature of the waste gas (H₁) and the utility consumption at the end of the chips cooling (H₂), HEX HU₁ and HEX HU₂ are likely to be redundant.

For the comparison of TACs, it is assumed that the investment costs of the initial design are already depreciated ($C_{cap} = 0$; reducing the TAC to the annual operating cost: $TAC = C_{Op,a}$). The HU demand is 1451 MWh/y and the CU demand 623 MWh/y. This results in annual operating costs of $C_{Op,a} = TAC = 141,080$ CHF/y. By investing $C_{cap} = 273,495$ CHF, respectively $C_{cap,a} = 35,419$ CHF/y with interest rate of $i_r 5\%$ over a depreciation lifetime of $n = 10$ y, HU and CU demand can be significantly reduced to 132 MWh/y and 55 MWh/y. This results in annual operating costs of $C_{Op,a} = 12,780$ CHF/y, reducing TAC by around 66% to 48,198 CHF/y. Such result is quite common for existing plants in industry which were not optimized for heat recovery. HR in such plants is often limited to pre-heating supply air with waste gas.

6.2. Performance and sensitivity analysis

Figure 8 shows the evolution of the previously discussed best found solution. The diagram shows the lowest TAC for each topology generation (comparing all TAC of the current population).

TAC is observed falling sharply initially, although stagnates over time. After around 50 topology generations, no improvement is noted. The convergence is highly dependent on parameters such as the number of possible HEX NE , the number of enthalpy stages NK , and the number of allowed HEX per split $\#E_{max}$. Therefore, in Table 2, the results of the sensitivity analysis on these parameters are shown. The experiments were performed under the Ockham's Razor principle, *plurality should not be posited without necessity*, meaning to keep the model as simple as necessary and not as accurate as possible. Hence, only reasonable parameter values are chosen to be investigated.

In the first experiment, the number of possible HEX NE is increased, starting with the two existing ones. It can be seen that the TAC are nearly similar to the initial design, meaning there is no room for improvement without adding additional HEX. By increasing NE , TAC can be reduced to a certain amount. However, the

Fig. 8. Convergence of the best found solution ($NE = 7$, $NK = 3$, $\#E_{\max} = 2$).

Table 2

Comparison of heat loads and areas between the best found solution and the initial solution.

Experiment	Parameter			Results	
	NE	NK	$\#E_{\max}$	TAC CHF/y	Δt s
Amount of possible HEX					
1	2	2	2	140,867	18,922
2	3	2	2	108,648	26,195
3	4	2	2	85,287	24,787
4	5	2	2	75,281	26,573
5	6	2	2	68,276	27,030
6	7	2	2	62,280	25,852
7	8	2	2	71,322	28,141
Number of enthalpy stages					
8	7	3	2	48,198	27,207
9	7	4	2	62,982	27,621
10	7	5	2	60,380	29,842
11	7	6	2	55,450	30,683
Number of enthalpy stages (splits with three HEX possible)					
12	7	2	3	63,305	29,628
13	7	3	3	65,967	27,812
14	7	4	3	59,141	28,915
15	7	5	3	57,357	30,481
16	7	6	3	63,231	30,362

reduction stagnates after five to six HEX. As expected, the computation time increases with increasing number of HEX due to the increase of optimization parameters.

For the next experiment, the number of enthalpy stages NK is increased (additional empty enthalpy stages with no existing heat exchanger matches were added to the initial design). Thereby, $NE = 7$ is the best solution found solution in this configuration. By increasing the NK , a slight increase in TAC , as well as in computation time is observed, with its best solution at $NK = 3$. The same experiment was performed but with an increase in the maximal possible HEX number in a split to $\#E_{\max} = 3$. The results are quite similar to $\#E_{\max} = 2$, however the computation time is increased by 5 to 10%. The results of these experiments are to be taken with

caution, as it is influenced by the randomness of the algorithm. However, the results are in a reasonable region.

Computation time is dependent on hardware and software. python was used for the software development which is an interpreted language. However, computation times could be improved by using a compiled language such as C++.

7. Conclusions

In this work, a two-level GA/DE algorithm for multi-period heat exchanger network retrofit was developed. For its application in industry, practical constraints are incorporated. The algorithm must handle soft streams, as well as streams which are only active in certain operating periods. Further practical constraints on the mixer temperatures to omit extreme temperatures (e.g. phase change or equipment constraints), or a maximum number of possible HEX in a split are implemented. In order to calculate the mixer temperature an explicit approach using the Lambert W-function is implemented. Piping usually has a significant impact on retrofit investment costs. Therefore, additional match costs are considered in the optimization.

The algorithm was successfully applied to an industrial case study, a frying process of two different potato chip variants. Thereby its application on a process with soft streams and partially existing streams is demonstrated. To achieve the retrofitted design, one of the existing heat exchangers is reused, one is removed, and six new heat exchangers are incorporated. The heat loads of the utility heat exchangers is reduced significantly resulting in a reduction of approximately 66% in its total annual cost. By performing a sensitivity analysis on the constraint parameters, it was found that the number of possible heat exchangers has the highest influence on reducing cost. An optimum in the total annual cost was found to require 7 possible heat exchangers. Increasing the number of enthalpy stages or increasing the number of possible heat exchangers within one split had a minor influence on the resulting cost. This suggests that the number of possible heat exchangers is the most important parameter for the optimization and has to be chosen carefully. By increasing the constraint parameters, the number of decision variables increases, as well resulting in higher computation times.

A high number of modifications is needed to get from the existing to the retrofitted design. Therefore, future work should investigate methods to limit the number of modifications on the network to give more flexibility to the user. A promising approach would be to switch to a simulated annealing algorithm for the topology optimization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jan A. Stampfli: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Writing – review & editing. **Benjamin H.Y. Ong:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Donald G. Olsen:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Beat Wellig:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **René Hofmann:** Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

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Appendix A. Application of the Lambert W-function to the logarithmic mean

The derivation for the application of the Lambert W-function, by Chen (2019) is slightly modified and updated to the here used variables below. The Lambert W-function is evaluated using Scipy Virtanen et al. (2020).

$$LMTD^{oc} = \frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc} - \Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}}\right)} \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} \tag{A.1}$$

$$\frac{LMTD^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} = \frac{\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} - 1}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}}\right)} \tag{A.2}$$

$$\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} = \exp\left(\left[\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} - 1\right] \frac{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}}{LMTD^{oc}}\right) \tag{A.3}$$

$$\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} \psi_2\right) = \exp(-\psi_2) \quad | \cdot (-\psi_2) \tag{A.4}$$

$$\underbrace{-\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} \psi_2}_x \exp\left(\underbrace{-\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} \psi_2}_x\right) = \underbrace{-\psi_2 \exp(-\psi_2)}_y \tag{A.5}$$

which can be substituted into the form of

$$x \exp(x) = y. \tag{A.6}$$

Thereby, the variable y is known and x unknown. By the use of the Lambert W-function x can be defined by

$$x = W(y) = W(x \exp(x)). \tag{A.7}$$

The application of Eq. (A.7) to right hand side Eq. (A.5) results in

$$-\frac{\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc}}{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}} \psi_2 = W(-\psi_2 \exp(-\psi_2)). \tag{A.8}$$

The temperature difference can be determined by

$$\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc} = -\frac{W(-\psi_2 \exp(-\psi_2))}{\psi_2} \Delta T_{e,2}^{oc} = \psi_1 \Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}. \tag{A.9}$$

Due to the fact, that W is ill-defined, the Lambert W-function has three possible branches (W_0^+ , W_0^- , and W_{-1}) which are depending on $y = -\psi_2 \exp(-\psi_2)$ respectively ψ_2 . The minimal value of y function is $y(\psi_2 = 1) = -\frac{1}{e}$ and thus, ψ_2 is always positive, the maximal value 0. Branch W_0^+ is only defined for $y > 1$. Therefore, the only decision on which branch the solution is, is depending on which side of the minimum in $y(\psi_2 = 1) = -\frac{1}{e}$ the solution is:

- W_0^- branch if $\psi_2 > 1$
- W_{-1} branch if $\psi_2 < 1$

For the case where $\psi_2 = 1 = \frac{\Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}}{LMTD^{oc}}$, the temperature difference over the whole heat exchanger is constant and therefore, $\Delta T_{e,1}^{oc} = \Delta T_{e,2}^{oc}$. Hence, the Lambert W-function is not needed.

Appendix B. Process requirements and cost data for the potato chips production case study

Table B.4
Utility data.

Utility	T_S °C	T_T °C	h W/(m ² K)	c_U CHF/MWh
Heating steam (HU)	300	299	5,000	80
Cooling water (CU)	0	1	2,000	40

Table B.3

Process requirements of the fritter line 1 for the regular chips and cractive chips OC.

Stream	#	T_S °C	T_T °C	$T_{extr.}$ °C	CP kW/K	h W/(m ² K)
Regular chips (4'410 h/y)						
Vapor heating	C ₁	136	229	500	2.51	400
Boiler air pre-heating	C ₂	10	40	300	1.52	100
Make-up oil pre-heating	C ₃	24	176	210	0.37	400
Degreaser air heating	C ₄	-	-	-	-	-
Degreaser direct steam evaporation	C ₅	-	-	-	-	-
Waste gas cooling*	H ₁	280	30	30	14.81	400
Chips cooling	H ₂	151	24	24	0.79	300
Cractive chips (2'610 h/y)						
Vapor heating	C ₁	125.9	226.1	500	2.45	400
Boiler air pre-heating	C ₂	10	40	300	1.48	100
Make-up oil pre-heating	C ₃	24	166	210	0.18	400
Degreaser air heating	C ₄	163.4	174	500	23.31	100
Degreaser direct steam evaporation	C ₅	144.9	145.1	145.1	940.00	5,000
Waste gas cooling*	H ₁	270.1	30	30	14.3	400
Chips cooling	H ₂	150	24	24	0.55	300

* Soft streams.

Table B.5

Modification cost factors (including Lang factors (Lang, 1948): 3 for adding equipment; 1.1 for removing equipment). Only cost for the removal of an equipment is listed, if it is existing (HEX, and admixer).

Equipment	C_0 CHF	Q [Q]	C_A CHF/Q	C_R CHF/Q	d_f –
HEX	0	A (m ²)	1,731	635	0.61
Split	0	–	40,000	–	1.00
Bypass	0	–	40,000	–	1.00
Admixer	0	–	40,000	14,666	1.00
Re-pipe	0	–	68,000	–	1.00
Re-sequence	0	–	68,000	–	1.00

Deprecation lifetime $n = 10$ y; interest rate $i_r = 5\%$.

Table B.6

Match cost matrix (including utility streams) in CHF.

H \ C	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	CU
H ₁	0	1,500	2,100	2,100	2,100	0
H ₂	900	3,000	600	300	300	0
HU	0	0	0	0	0	0

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